

An Analysis on the Factors which Influence the Development of Central Business District (CBD) Property Polonia, Medan

Markus Tarigan¹, Nazaruddin Matondang², Dwira Nirfalini Aulia²

¹Postgraduate Students at Universitas Sumatera Utara, Indonesia

²Postgraduate Lecturer at Universitas Sumatera Utara, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Markus Tarigan

ABSTRACT

The objective of the research was to prove the influence of the variables of location and accessibility, socio-economy, the availability of facility, and land use on the development of central business district (CBD) Property Polonia, Medan. The phenomenon in the research location was that there was still low activity in goods and services which was different from its strategic location which should be the attraction for the people surrounding it and the people in Medan in general as the place for the economic, social, and cultural activities. Besides that, it is located beside the of air force complex. The research used correlation research method which studied the correlation of two or more variables to find out how far the variation of the correlation. There were 90 samples consisted of the owners of store houses and the person who was in charge of the operation of the store houses. The result of the research showed that, simultaneously, the variables of location and accessibility, socio-economy, the availability of facility, and land use had positive and significant influence on the development of central business district (CBD) Property Polonia, Medan.

Keywords: Location and Accessibility, Socio-Economy, The Availability of Facility, Land Use, Central Business District (CBD)

INTRODUCTION

The area of the former Polonia Airport Medan which is located close to the upper middle housing environment and based on the area in the community field around the former Polonia Airport Medan is a community with high income categories, thus making this area much glance by the developers or property developers to invest in the region. One of the concepts that have been developed in Jakarta Capital is superblock or also known as the central business district which is further abbreviated as CBD. The central business district (CBD) or the event centre area (DPK) is a small part of the city which is the centre of all political, social, cultural, economic, and technology.

The opportunity to build a CBD in the area is the former Polonia Airport Medan is not wasted by the developers in the city of Medan, where the CBD area is built by PT. Multatuli Group with building a CBD complex in the city of Medan in a considerable area that is 337,000 square meters of land located in the elite residential area and adjacent to the neighborhood of TNI AU Polonia headquarters, known Name of CBD Polonia Medan.

Source: Google Maps (2017)

Figure 1. Location of Central Business District (CBD) Property Polonia, Medan

Unlike Sudirman Central Business District (SCBD) in the capital city of Jakarta, Sudirman Central Business District (SCBD) is located between the two main streets of Jendral Sudirman and Gatot Subroto Street which is the southern part of the golden triangle of Jakarta. The entrance to SCBD is relatively easy and accessible by the public transportation system. The area that is built and managed by PT. Danayasa Arthatama TBK covers an area of 45 hectares and 13 hectares of land destined for infrastructure facilities. SCBD has become a pioneer in the CBD in Indonesia that brings offices, retail, hotels, hospitals, and world-class life style facilities. SCBD presents the concept of integrating public spaces, apartment complexes, hotels, condominiums, shopping centers, and recreational facilities.

The location factor can be regarded as the strongest factor in its influence on the value of a property (Maria, 2017). The father of the location theory, Von Thunen in Putri (2011), suggested that the most expensive land rental rates were at the center of the market and were getting lower when away from the market. The development of Von Thunen theory is in addition to the high price in the city center and will be decreasing when the farther away from the city center. The success of a property business such as CBD is determined by the selection of precise and strategic locations. Accessibility is one of the factors that greatly affects whether a

suatulation is interesting to visit or not. The level of accessibility is the level of ease in reaching and towards a location is reviewed by other areas of the area (Putri, 2011). According to Putri, the level of accessibility is influenced by distance, the condition of the Nexus infrastructure, the availability of various linkages, the availability of various connecting facilities including its frequency and the level of security and convenience to go through the line. Inbound and outgoing access to Polonia CBD is relatively difficult because it is not located near the city center where there is no public transportation system in the area and must be through the headquarters of the TNI AU. Economic actors in activities usually choose the location at strategic Tempatempatyang in most areas of the city.

Economic actors will try to make goods or services sold by buyers. Strategic and favorable locations in the center of the city or in a location that is the location of community activities become the main choice. There can be the presence of economic activity perpetrators around the location of trading activities, education, offices, and other social activities of society. In the theory of location also mentioned that for traders there is a tendency to orientated to the concentration of consumers in determining the location of the business (Sidik, 2000). Economic activity in question in this research is the activity of economic actors who have a tendency to be in the research, namely the buyers of property in

CBD Polonia Medan that enables the property that has been purchased.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Location and Accessibility

The location factor determines whether a property is easy or difficult to achieve. The property which has its location within the city can be easily reached as there is a better transportation system than the city's outer quarter.

Accessibility is what determines the value of a property in the region near a property with the CBD area then the cost of a person to an event (CBD) will be smaller too, where the smaller the cost of accessibility further increases the profit so that it will cause the value of the property that lies in the high-value CBD because its accessibility costs are relatively small compared to areas far from the CBD area (Prawoto, 2010). Accessibility is how to reach a desired place from a single location, it is related to the availability of public transportation, the condition of the road to a distance to a place, e.g. to the place of education, recreation places, markets, health facilities and others.

2.2 Socio-Economy

According to research by Widhaswara (2015) who conducted research on the Galaxy Bumi Permai, Surabaya, the factors that determine the values of a property are:

- a. Requests indicating the wishes and abilities of a person to purchase or rent a property.
- b. Uses that show the benefits of the subject property that could provide satisfaction to the consumer.
- c. Scarcity indicating the quantity and quality of another property that rivals the subject property concerned.
- d. Transferability, indicating the process of transferring property rights Darisatu party to another through sale and purchase, lease, and contract.

In addition to economic factors, there are also socialistic factors affecting the values and building of a property, for example:

a. Number of Inhabitants

The population has an impact on many areas of the region, which affects the value of the building in the Galaxi Bumi Permai property, Surabaya.

b. Population Density

The density of the population, which is correlated with the amount of manpower, wage rate, income level and purchasing power, has an effect on the demand and supply of goods or services products.

c. Level of Education

The level of education is one variable that can show the characteristics of people who will then determine the pattern of land use in a business district.

d. Crime or Security Levels

Properties whose security level is not guaranteed will reduce the interest of people to occupy the housing. Lack of interest in the property must have a low value of sales.

2.3 The Availability of Facility

Public facilities of CBD are everything provided to support in delivering services that should not be forgotten in the design of the provision of physical equipment to provide convenience to the consumers to carry out activities so that the needs of consumers are fulfilled (Kotler, 2007).

Public facilities in the property are everything provided by the developer in supporting the convenience of its users, the form of physical completion to provide convenience to consumers to carry out activities so that the needs of buyers can be fulfilled. With good facilities and adequate, it will provide positive values for consumers if there is a deficiency in the other. The more complete the facilities offered will be the higher the property's Pulanilai. The facilities provided by the developer have influenced the development of the property, because closely related to the establishment of buyer's perception.

2.4 Land Use

Land use is one of the tools of the elements of the field designing, to determine the planning of two dimensionality that will then determine the three-dimensional space. The determination of land Use can create a relationship between land utilization and infrastructure functions such as roads, utilities up to the environment of circulation or parking layout. In principle, land use is a setting for use to determine the best option in allocating certain functions, so that in general it can give an overall picture of how the area in the area should work.

Indafa'a (2006) conducted research on planning and designing the CBD of Simpang Lima Gumul Monument with the arrangement of areas concerned with the role of function and meaning of the region. CBDSimpang Lima Area Planning Gumul Monument is geared towards utilizing land use and new land use processing which can fulfill service function in Kediri district.

2.5 Central Business District (CBD)

CBD is the core of the city of trade, culture and cultural. The CBD is formed from the locations of adjacent activities and is easily reached by transport or pedestrian. In a certain scale, the CBD becomes superblock, and not only has the function of trading, service and culture, but it increases with various other functions such as occupancy, place of education, recreation, hospital, hotel, exhibition hall and other.

The development of superblock aims to reduce congestion by the movement of people who need close-up mobility, so there is no need to exit the Superblock (Tondobala, 2015). The concept of

superblock, namely to encourage the growth of activities that are integrated in a container adequately, producing a system of Saranadan more efficient and economical infrastructure, improving the circulation system, encouraging the development of the system of the rigid and more flexible, encouraging a clear separation between the various modes of transportation and provide a broad framework for the innovation of building design and environment (Kamil, 2008).

RESEARCH METHODS

It is located beside the Air Force Complex, Property Polonia, Medan.

The research used correlation research method which studied the correlation of two or more variables to find out how far the variation of the correlation.

There were 90 samples consisted of the owners of store houses and the person who was in charge of the operation of the store houses.

RESULT

F Test

The F test or simultaneous test is to know the extent to which the effects of free variables are influenced jointly against the dependent variable.

The development of the area in the CBD Polonia Medan or research area.

The F test is done to take conclusions on the value of the signification of the influence of free variables against bonded variables. The F-count value of a regression model for a the development of central business district (CBD) (Y) variable can be seen from 1:

Table 1. Simultaneous Test or F Test Results
ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.470	4	3.118	7.911	.000 ^a
	Residual	21.676	55	.394		
	Total	34.146	59			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Location and Accessibility, Socio-Economy, The Availability ofFacility, Land Use

b. Dependent Variable: Central Business District (CBD)

Result of F test obtained the value of significance is 0.000 smaller than the significance of the research decree 0.05 then it could be concluded that simultaneously or together that all the independent variables of location and accessibility, socio-economy, the availability of facility, and land use had positive and significant influence on the development of central business district (CBD) Property Polonia, Medan.

The hypothesis in this study was that there was a positive relationship and the simultaneous meaning of location and accessibility, socio-economy, the availability of facility, and land use. As well as, there is a partial positive and significant variation of each of the variable-free variables. The test result-F states means that it has the same simultaneous or concomitant effect of a variable built to the development of the region with a value of calculated significance that is 0.000 a. This F-test result supports earlier research in previous chapters, the research conducted by Suwanto (2011) Where the research results stated that a superblock has an important role in improving the quality of urban environment in its region, as well as other environment around its area, the entrance and exit of the Superblock area will be relatively easy to accelerate the development of the area, so that the influence of location and accessibility are important in the growth of the

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The result of the research showed that, simultaneously, the variables of location and accessibility, socio-economy, the availability of facility, and land use had positive and significant influence on the development of central business district (CBD) Property Polonia, Medan.

Based on the results of the study, the following suggestions can be obtained:

1. For academics, the next research should be added that affect the development of the central business district (CBD) Polonia area.

2. Government in the CBD area of Polonia Medan need to revisit the spatial layout and Recana details layout of the city in the central business District Polonia Medan, so with the area of CBD Polonia Medan can become a business icon and new entertainment in the city of Medan.

3. Based on the instruments used in this research variable, the developer's need to note is as follows:

a. Need to coordinate with the relevant parties in presenting the public routes as access to facilitate the community visiting the CBD Polonia Medan.

b. The developer or developer, must be innovative in the economic, social and cultural events as the attraction of public visits as they complement and build facilities according to site Plan and area requirements called the CBD.

REFERENCES

1. Indafa'a, Nurlaila. (2006). *Perencanaan dan Perancangan CBD Simpang Lima Gulum di Kabupaten Kediri*. Jurnal Arsitektur, Universitas Sebelas Maret Surakarta.
2. Kamil, Ridwan. (2008). *Superblok sebagai Model Kendali Pembangunan Kota*. <http://ridwankamil.wordpress.com/2008/09/27>, accessed 4 Desember 2016.
3. Kotler. Philip. (2007). *Manajemen Pemasaran Perspektif Asia*. Yogyakarta: Salemba Empat.
4. Maria. (2017). *Dampak Struktur Demografi Terhadap Pertumbuhan Perumahan di Kota Bandung*. Jurnal Ekonomi, Universitas Katolik Parahyangan Bandung.
5. Putri, Imaniar. (2011). *Optimalisasi Nilai Properti Kawasan Perumahan Puri Anjasmoro Berdasarkan Faktor Berpengaruh*. Jurnal Teknik, Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
6. Prawoto, Agus. (2010). *Teori Dan Praktek Penilaian Properti*. Yogyakarta: BPFE Universitas Gadjah Mada.
7. Sidik, Ignas. (2000). *Pemasaran Stratejik dan Strategi Pemasaran*. Jurnal Forum Manajemen Prasetya Mulya, 72(14):14-19.
8. Suwanto, Hajar. (2011). *Perkembangan Superblok dalam Perspektif Investasi Bidang Properti di Kawasan Asia Pasifik*.

Jurnal Arsitektur, Universitas Sumatera Utara Medan

Institut Teknologi Sepuluh November Surabaya.

9. Tondobala, Linda. (2015). *Pengembangan Struktur Ruang: Mereduksi Mobilitas Perkotaan*. Media Matrasain.
10. Widhaswara. (2015). *Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Nilai Tanah dan Bangunan pada Suatu Properti*. Jurnal Ekonomi Kota,

How to cite this article: Tarigan M, Matondang N, Aulia DN. An analysis on the factors which influence the development of central business district (CBD) property Polonia, Medan. International Journal of Research and Review. 2020; 7(6): 447-452.
